

techno-centric home healthcare has been integrated into mathematical optimization models and solution approaches. Additionally, we propose potential research directions by exploring optimization problems that may arise from the use of technologies in HHC that have not yet been fully addressed in the literature.

3 - Multiperiod stochastic optimization with machine learning for dynamic home healthcare routing

Louise Tassin, Véronique François, Elise Vandomme, Yasemin Arda

Home healthcare (HHC) is gaining popularity as a means of alleviating pressure on healthcare systems and improving patient well-being. However, effective HHC operations require optimized resource utilization, a challenge complicated by inherent uncertainty and dynamism. Although deterministic variants of the home healthcare routing and scheduling problem have been extensively studied, this is not the case of stochastic and dynamic versions. Aiming to address this gap, our work analyzes the problem of a home healthcare provider (HHCP) making daily decisions regarding the acceptance of new patient requests that arrive dynamically over the planning horizon. The HHCP also has to assign the first visit of each accepted patient to a day. It is assumed that every patient needs at least one visit and a specific periodicity of care, but the total number of visits that a patient will effectively require is stochastic. However, the HHCP must commit to serving accepted patients for their total number of visits. Moreover, the HHCP creates routes for the available caregivers in order to cover the visits planned for the current day. The problem is modeled as a Markov decision process. We will outline a solution approach that integrates machine learning techniques with traditional combinatorial optimization algorithms. This hybrid approach aims to effectively tackle the stochasticity inherent in the patients arrival process and care duration.

4 - Optimizing Digital Health Services in Primary Care: A Data-Driven Approach to Value Assessment

Mariana Peyroteo, António Grilo, Luís Lapão

Multimorbidity places increasing demands on primary healthcare (PHC), requiring coordinated and patient-centred care. Digital Health Services (DHS) offer promising solutions, yet there is a lack of structured models to estimate their value in real-world PHC settings. This study aimed to develop and apply a decision framework to estimate the value of a DHS in PHC, using the METHIS platform. METHIS supports Goal-Oriented Care by enabling patients and professionals to collaboratively define and monitor individual health goals. The framework combines Design Science Research and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to integrate clinical data, Patient-Reported Outcomes, and service utilisation across three value domains: quality, service, and cost. A six-month pilot currently underway in seven PHC units in Lisbon, involving 20 professionals (10 doctors and 10 nurses) and 20 patients, will generate the real-world data required to estimate value. Early feedback indicates improved goal alignment, strengthened communication, and high system usability. This framework provides a structured, participatory approach to value estimation, illustrating how operations research can support the implementation of Value-Based Healthcare through measurable and actionable insights.

In many organizations, human resources are a primary cost driver, making careful scheduling of this resource paramount. Within this context, shift design and scheduling emerge as key planning tasks. The shift design problem devises a set of workable shifts based on the staffing requirements. Then, the shift scheduling problem assembles these shifts to a shift schedule. Traditionally, shift design and scheduling are treated as separate problems. This separation ignores synergies between the shift design and scheduling, leading to inefficiencies when relying on predetermined shift designs. Therefore, we introduce an integrated approach for shift design and rotating workforce scheduling. In addition to the shift design objective function, we model an ergonomics objective function for the quality of the schedule. We solve the integrated problem using a branch-and-cut approach based on a compact formulation and graph representation, ensuring feasibility of shift designs by modeling the schedule as a Eulerian cycle of work and rest sequences. Results show that an integrated shift design and scheduling enables shift schedules with improved ergonomics without deteriorating the shift design objective compared to the sequential planning approach. Further, an analysis of the Pareto-efficient frontiers across the benchmark set indicates that substantial improvements in ergonomics are possible if decision makers are willing to accept a minor reduction in shift design quality.

2 - Logic-Based Benders Decomposition for a labour constrained production scheduling problem

Johanna Mlekusch, Carla Juvin, Christian Artigues, Richard Hartl

In modern project and production management, efficiently allocating limited resources to tasks is a critical challenge. This research is motivated by a production problem in the screen-printing industry, modelled as the Dual-Resource-Constrained Re-entrant Flexible Flow Shop, an extension of the Re-entrant Flow Shop Problem. In addition, the problem involves a heterogeneous, multi-skilled workforce, and machines require skilled workers to operate throughout the processing time. As a result, the schedule must not only adhere to precedence constraints but also account for resource limitations while ensuring that tasks are assigned to workers with the necessary skills. Previous research has proposed a constraint programming model and a hybrid genetic algorithm to tackle large problem instances, yielding feasible solutions within a short time frame. This study introduces a novel exact solution method based on Logic-Based-Benders decomposition. The proposed decomposition method is evaluated against the constraint programming model for the integrated problem on a set of small instances. Preliminary results indicate that the proposed method outperforms the constraint programming approach by proving optimality in more cases and within a shorter time frame while also providing tighter bounds for instances that could not be solved to proven optimality.

3 - Navigating Turbulence: Near Real Time Rescheduling of Crew Rosters in Short-Haul Aviation

Louisa Sober, Ruth Walton, Michael Sutherland

In the aviation industry, any disruptions to crew rosters can cause a cascade of knock-on effects which impact both crew and scheduled flights. In order to navigate the many regulations and operational constraints, highly trained crewing teams are required to rapidly reconfigure the shifts to minimise disruptions. During busy periods the volume of disruptions can overwhelm crewing teams, potentially resulting in regulatory violations, further delays, cancellations and even fines.

In early 2024 we were tasked with developing and deploying a crew rescheduling tool for a short-haul airline to support the crewing team during the upcoming busy summer period. Within a rapid 5 month timeline, we progressed through a full project pipeline from initial scoping to a fully deployed user interface that updated in near real time and which has been adopted into daily operations.

This talk will look into the metaheuristic approach that formed the core of our solution which facilitated rapid and intelligent roster reconfiguration. We will also discuss the inclusion of an explainability layer which provided the rationale behind these recommendations and enhanced user understanding and adoption.

In addition we will address the essential supporting elements that ensured the adoption of the solution. This includes strong stakeholder

■ WB-12

Wednesday, 10:30-12:00 - Room: Clarendon SR 1.02

Workforce scheduling

Stream: Scheduling and Project Management
Invited session

Chair: [Johanna Mlekusch](#)

1 - Enhancing Ergonomics by Integrated Shift Design and Rotating Workforce Scheduling

Tristan Becker